

European Nucleotide Archive

Environmental DNA Standards and Data Submission

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ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Data sharing

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Interoperability
- Reproducibility/Reusability
- Data standards
- Community collaboration

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- Reusability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

Data Structure at ENA

ENA Data Structure

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:

“I want to see data from fungi...

... collected in Argentina ...

... between April and June ...

... compared with the same in Costa Rica”

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

ENA Metadata Model: Study

- Tropical coastal lagoons are important ecosystems supporting high levels of biodiversity and ecosystem services.
- Monitoring of benthic biodiversity and detection of harmful or invasive species in two tropical coastal lagoons in Mexico through eDNA metabarcoding.
- Benthic diversity showed pattern evidencing transition from freshwater to seawater.
- Detection of harmful, invasive, non-indigenous species, bioindicators and species of commercial importance.

By Jaumahell - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0,
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=30392578>

By Microphotograph taken by G. Carter - Obtained from
<http://www.glerl.noaa.gov/pubs/photogallery/Waterlife/pages/0686.html>, Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=2143998>

ENA Metadata Model: Study

ENA Metadata Model: Study

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ENA Webin Submissions Portal Support Manage Account Log

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Short descriptive study title *

Study Name

Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations

Study Attributes

Add Study Attributes

ENA Metadata Model: Study

EMBL-EBI Services Research Training About us EMBL-EBI

ENA Webin Submissions Portal Support Manage Account Log

Register study (project)

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
31-03-2027

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
Short descriptive study title *

Study Name
Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration
Add PubMed Citations +

Study Attributes
Add Study Attributes +

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

- Lagoons divided in zones and 3 samples collected from each zone.
- Sediment samples were collected with a Petite Ponar grab in the end of the dry season and in the end of the rainy season.
- Additional environmental data collected from each sampling site.
- Each sample was homogenized and stored at -20°C .

Gomez-Garrido et al, DNA Research (2023),
doi.org/10.1093/dnares/dsad008

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

113 sediment samples registered from the two lagoons and collection dates

Biosample: [SAMEA14416814](#)

Corralero coastal lagoon sediment sample number 8, dry season

Sample

Location: Corralero
Season: rainy season
Depth: 1.4
Sample: CR24

Sample

Location: Corralero
Season: dry season
Depth: 1.3
Sample: CD8

Sample

Location: Chacahua
Season: rainy
Depth: 1.4
Sample: CHR12

Sample

Location: Chacahua
Season: dry
Depth: 2.8
Sample: CHR41

Organism: sediment metagenome
Scientific Name: sediment metagenome
Sample Accession: SAMEA14416814
Location: 16.24544444 N 98.18488889 W
Center Name: UNIVERSIDAD DEL MAR
Sample Alias: Corralero-Chacahua6
Checklist: ERC000021
Sample Title: CD8
Geographic Location (Depth): 1.3

ENA-CHECKLIST: ERC000021

Environment (Material): Soil, mud, sand
Collection Date: 2018-03-10
Geographic Location (Longitude): -98.18488889
Sediment Environmental Package: sediment
Geographic Location (Latitude): 16.24544444
Geographic Location (Elevation): 0
Investigation Type: eukaryote

ENA Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000020	GSC MixS plant associated	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000021	GSC MixS sediment	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000022	GSC MixS soil	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000023	GSC MixS wastewater sludge	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000024	GSC MixS water	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.

ENA Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

ENA Sample Checklist Groups

Please select a checklist group first.

Environmental Checklists This group currently includes Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) MixS sample checklists

Marine Checklists This group currently includes Micro B3 and Tara Oceans sample checklists

Other Checklists This group currently includes the ENA default sample checklist and a few project specific checklists

Pathogens Checklists This group currently includes several prokaryote and virus pathogen sample checklists

[Back](#)

[Next](#)

ENA Metadata Model: Sample – GSC MixS sediment

You have selected **GSC MixS sediment**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is Homo sapiens.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None	The date the sample was collected with the intention of sequencing, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid ISO8601 compliant times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (latitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (longitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by longitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system

ENA Metadata Model: Sample – GSC MixS sediment

You have selected **GSC MixS sediment**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	trophic level	Permitted values	None	Trophic levels are the feeding position in a food chain. Microbes can be a range of producers (e.g. chemolithotroph)
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed biotic relationship	Permitted values	None	Description of relationship(s) between the subject organism and other organism(s) it is associated with. E.g., parasite on species X; mutualist with species Y. The target organism is the subject of the relationship, and the other organism(s) is the object.
<input type="checkbox"/>	known pathogenicity	Text field	None	To what is the entity pathogenic, for instance plant, fungi, bacteria
<input type="checkbox"/>	relationship to oxygen	Permitted values	None	Is this organism an aerobe, anaerobe? Please note that aerobic and anaerobic are valid descriptors for microbial environments
<input type="checkbox"/>	propagation	Text field	None	The type of reproduction from the parent stock. Values for this field is specific to different taxa. For phage or virus: lytic/lysogenic/temperate/obligately lytic. For plasmids: incompatibility group. For eukaryotes: sexual/asexual. Mandatory for MIGs of eukaryotes, plasmids and viruses.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device	Text field	None	The device used to collect an environmental sample. It is recommended to use terms listed under environmental sampling device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO) and/or terms listed under specimen collection device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0002094).

The Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- Recommended and optional fields are encouraged to provide maximum metadata for samples
- Custom Fields bar enables users to add custom sample attributes
- More metadata = more easily searchable and readable data

ENA Web Submission Portal

Register Samples using spreadsheet template

Download spreadsheet to register samples

Please select the most appropriate checklist group, checklist and checklist fields. Download an empty spreadsheet template, fill in the spreadsheet and submit the spreadsheet using Webin.

Select checklist group: ENA Native Microarray Checklist

Select checklist: ENA Native Microarray Checklist

Select checklist fields: ENA Native Microarray Checklist

Download spreadsheet template

You have selected ENA Native Microarray Checklist. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Recommended Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device or method	Text field	None	The method or device employed for collecting the sample
<input type="checkbox"/>	location and growth condition	Text field	None	Publication reference in the form of PubMed ID (pmid), digital object identifier (doi) or url for location and growth condition specifications of the organism/culture. Mandatory for WGS and RNA-SEQ. Specimens
<input type="checkbox"/>	amount or size of sample collected	Integer expression	Liquid/LCM	Amount or size of sample (volume, mass or array) that was collected
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage duration	Integer expression	None/Hours/days/weeks/months	Duration for which sample was stored
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage temperature	Integer expression	°C	Temperature at which sample was stored. (e.g. -80)
<input type="checkbox"/>	growth condition	Text field	None	A text field to record any specific media/culture conditions used to grow organisms or parts of the organism. This includes incubated environments such as cultures and open environments such as field studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	temperature	Integer expression	°C	Temperature of water at the time of taking the sample. Format: int, min, max, P10 (75, 100, 100, 100, 100, 100, 100, 100, 100, 100)

The Metadata Model: Sample - Taxonomy

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- ▼ metagenomes
- ▼ ecological metagenomes
 - activated carbon metagenome [species]
 - activated sludge metagenome [species]
 - aerosol metagenome [species]
 - air metagenome [species]
 - alkal sediment metagenome [species]
 - anaerobic digester metagenome [species]
 - archaeline metagenome [species]
 - ant fungus garden metagenome [species]
 - aquaculture metagenome [species]
 - aquatic metagenome [species]
 - aquifer metagenome [species]
 - ballast water metagenome [species]
 - beach sand metagenome [species]

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- ▼ metagenomes
- > ecological metagenomes
 - metagenome [species]
- ▼ organismal metagenomes
 - algae metagenome [species]
 - amphibian metagenome [species]
 - annelid metagenome [species]
 - ant metagenome [species]
 - aquatic viral metagenome [species]
 - bat metagenome [species]
 - beetle metagenome [species]
 - bird metagenome [species]
 - blood metagenome [species]
 - bovine gut metagenome [species]
 - bovine metagenome [species]

View: XML
Download: XML
Navigation: Show
Tax Tree: Hide
Related ENA Records: Show

View: XML
Download: XML
Navigation: Show
Tax Tree: Hide
Related ENA Records: Show

- The taxon ID is an essential attribute of your ENA samples
- Make sure you use environmental taxonomy

Sediment metagenome

Taxonomy ID: 749907

Scientific name: **sediment metagenome**

Inherited blast name: **metagenomes**

Rank: **species**

metagenome

Taxonomy ID: 256318

Scientific name: **metagenome**

Inherited blast name: **metagenomes**

Rank: **species**

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

- DNA was extracted from 10 g of each homogenized sediment sample
- Two regions were amplified and sequenced on a Illumina MiSeq using the V3 2 × 300 bp Illumina sequencing kit (Illumina):
 - V4 region of the 18S rRNA gene
 - partial fragment of COI

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

ENA Metadata Model: Run

ENA Metadata Model: Run

The 113 experiments hold paired fastq files.

These are compressed and uploaded to a database, where they undergo processing and wait to be made public.

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATATCAGTTTCCTTTGTGATGGGGCGTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTATGGAAGTGCACCCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTTGCTAT
TGTGAAGTTA
+
=?AD=D?FDB??ACGHGGEHCEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEACHIID>EEC>A3@D;?=:ABCA?
@@A8=B=B>89>ACCCACCADC3@4@@A
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGGTGAGGAGAACAATAAAAATGATACCTTCATTTAATTATCATTTAGA
GATGATATC
+
CCCFDFFHHHHIJIJJJJJJJJJJII?
DGIJJJBFHIFGGGIJIJJJJHHHHFFFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTTAAACAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTGTAATCTACTAGCAAAAACCTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAGATATTGATACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCCCFFFFHDDFFGHHHJIIJJIIJJIIJJIIJIGHIIJJJJIIJJIIJJJJJJIGJIHGHHHHHFFFFFFFEDCCACDDEEEDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAAGTATCAAAA
ATTTGCAGCA
+
@=?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?BB9BFGHIDF@===FCGEGGGH3AEHC;@DDF@C>;A@AC:
5-5;>@C@CCC::@ACBA@C:4>:(2
```

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

Metadata Model: Read Submission Checklist

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample		Sample alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study		Study alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name		The name for the library if any.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values	The type of source material that is being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values	The method used to select for or against, enrich, or screen the material being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values	The sequencing technique intended for this library.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values	The library layout specifies whether to expect single or paired configuration of reads.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project description and metadata

Project: PRJEB52950

Tropical coastal lagoons are important ecosystems that support high levels of biodiversity and provide several goods and services. Monitoring of benthic biodiversity and detection of harmful or invasive species is crucial, particularly in relation to seasonal and spatial variation of environmental conditions. In this study, eDNA metabarcoding was used in two tropical coastal lagoons, Chachahua (CH) and Corralero (C) (Southern Mexican Pacific), to describe the benthic biodiversity and its spatial-temporal dynamics. The distribution of benthic diversity within the lagoons showed a very particular pattern evidencing a transition from freshwater to seawater. Although the two lagoon systems are similar in terms of the species composition of metazoans and microeukaryotes, our findings indicate that they are different in taxa richness and structure, resulting in regional partitioning of the diversity with salinity as the driving factor of community composition in CH. Harmful, invasive, non-indigenous species, bioindicators and species of commercial importance were detected, demonstrating the reach of this technique for biodiversity monitoring along with the continued efforts of building species reference libraries.

Show More

Secondary Study Accession: ERP137703

Study Title: Monitoring of benthic eukaryotic communities in two tropical coastal lagoons through eDNA metabarcoding: a spatial and temporal approximation

Center Name: UNIVERSIDAD DEL MAR

Study Name: Monitoring of benthic eukaryotic communities in two tropical coastal lagoons through eDNA metabarcoding

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2022-09-15

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Navigate around the object

Data

Read Files: Hide

Navigate on data

Run-centric data table

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script Download selected files

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP
PRJEB52950	SAMEA14416828	ERX9575323	ERR10034959	749907	sediment metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10034959_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10034959_2.fastq.gz
PRJEB52950	SAMEA14416830	ERX9575325	ERR10034961	749907	sediment metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10034961_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10034961_2.fastq.gz

Information for a single run

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

 View: XML
XML (STUDY)

 Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

 Cross References: Show

 ORCID Data Claims: Show

 Related ENA Records: Show

Data

 Read Files: Hide

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project: PRJEB52950

Tropical coastal lagoons are important ecosystems that support high levels of biodiversity and provide several goods and services. Monitoring of benthic biodiversity and detection of harmful or invasive species is crucial, particularly in relation to seasonal and spatial variation of environmental conditions. In this study, eDNA metabarcoding was used in two tropical coastal lagoons, Chacahua (CH) and Corralero (C) (Southern Mexican Pacific), to describe the benthic biodiversity and its spatial-temporal dynamics. The distribution of benthic diversity within the lagoons showed a very particular pattern evidencing a transition from freshwater to seawater. Although the two lagoon systems are similar in terms of the species composition of metazoans and microeukaryotes, our findings indicate that they are different in taxa richness and structure, resulting in regional partitioning of the diversity with salinity as the driving factor of community composition in CH. Harmful, invasive, non-indigenous species, bioindicators and species of commercial importance were detected, demonstrating the reach of this technique for biodiversity monitoring along with the continued efforts of building species reference libraries.

Show More

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ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2022-09-15

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Experiment	113
Run	113

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: ERX9575307

Illumina MiSeq paired end sequencing

Organism: [sediment metagenome](#)
Experiment Accession: ERX9575307
Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA
Instrument Model: Illumina MiSeq
Center Name: UNIVERSIDAD DEL MAR
Library Layout: PAIRED
Library Strategy: AMPLICON
Library Source: METAGENOMIC
Library Name: unspecified
Library Selection: PCR
Run Accession: ERR10034943

Show Less

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP
PRJEB52950	SAMEA14416812	ERX9575307	ERR10034943	749907	sediment metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR10034943_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> ERR10034943_2.fastq.gz

General

View: XML
Download: XML
Cross References: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

Tags

environment by geolocation
terrestrial

New tags feature

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

```
>ENA|PEHZ01000001|PEHZ01000001.1 Insect metagenome contig_0_374_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GATACGTTGTCAGGTGCAAGGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATG
TGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGGAAGTGTGTGTGCATGGAGGATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTA
TGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGGGT
GTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGTCAGGTGCAA
GGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTG
AGGGTGTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGTCAGG
TCAAGGGTATGTG
>ENA|PEHZ01000002|PEHZ01000002.1 Insect metagenome contig_2_497_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATACTAGGGTTAAAATACCCTAAAGTAGAAGCAAAAAGTTA
ATATATTAACCGCATAACTATGAGATACTATTTCTCTGTTATGAAAATGATTAAGGATTAG
TATGAGAATCTACGGGTTTTCTATTTTCATCTGAGTTTATGCTGGAGTCTTATATATCTA
TTTTAACGAGAATAAAGAAACCCTAGATACTTTTTATAACACAAGAGATATTAACAATTT
CTATTCACGTTTTATTTAGTAGGTATGAATTAAGAACTATCTAAGATTCAATTAATTCAT
AATGAAAGAAAATGAATGGTTAGAAAAAGAAAATAAAAACTTTCATTTACTTCTAGAATC
TGGTAGTAACCTAATAGAGATGATAATTTGATTAATCATGCCAAAGATTATAGCGGAGTT
AAAAATAGTGAAGTAAAAATTGACCGATTTGAGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTCCGGGTAGGTG
GAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000003|PEHZ01000003.1 Insect metagenome contig_4_469_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATCATTGCGCTAAATGCAAGTTCTGGATGCTTGTGGACTT
TTCCATGAAGTGATGTTTCTCCATCATCGCACAGTCAATGTTGTACGCGAATCAGGAATC
GTAGTCGATTGACTACCGAGTCACTCATCGGGCTCGACTGTGCGATGAACATAATCGTG
TCTGATGCATGAAAGGTACTGGGCCAATTTGTGCGACGAAATTTGAAAGTACGCGCTACC
TCAGGAATCATCGGTGTGGAACTTTGTAAAAATCAGTGTGTCATTTATCAAGACGCT
TTGAAAGGGCCGATCCGCGCCAGGGTCTTTAAGCTCAGTATTTGCCACAGTATCAGAA
AACCGGCAATACTAAACAGACCCGCTGCTGGCTTTGATAAATCCTTCCAAACAGGCCCT
TCTTGGTCATTTGATCGAAATGGGGCTGCGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000004|PEHZ01000004.1 Insect metagenome contig_8_628_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACTCAACCCCTCAAGGTGATTCGTAGCTCAAAAATACCCAC
TATCGCTATCGTAATGAATTTCTATCTTGAATCTCACTACCTGGTTTTTTCAGCGGCTTTAAJ
```

CUTADAPT was used for demultiplexing and primer removal. Quality and size filtering was also performed.

Sequences were dereplicated and MOTUs were clustered with USEARCH.

Taxonomic identification was made against reference databases (INSDC and BOLD).

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

COI Data availability

Raw sequence data was uploaded to the European Nucleotide Archive under the project accession: PRJEB52950.

Environmental data and OTU tables are uploaded as Supplementary Information.

#OTU	table	OTUId	CD10																																							
OTU_21	1087																																									
OTU_36	223	60	152	5	13	0	0	0	66	5	1	0	0	1	3	0	2	1	2	0	7	6	0	11	40																	
OTU_97	16	16	19	1	3	0	0	1	3	3	0	0	0	3	3	0	7	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3																	
OTU_9	318	226	238	678	82	0	9	2	6	73	15	20	0	21	2	0	21	0	6	0	25	28	0	8	142																	
OTU_5	204	134	0	82	4	6065	9586	2	0	34	314	27	22	2442	994	0	16	0	43	2	0	0	0	0																		
OTU_164	13	2	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3																	
OTU_25	218	62	93	38	32	2	9	0	8	100	3	8	0	12	10	0	21	0	23	0	22	13	0	8	61																	
OTU_35	3	0	1	0	65	0	0	0	0	0	0	87	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	11	21	4	0	0	0																	
OTU_17	29	27	19	5	2	1	4	0	2	9	2	0	0	1	0	0	7	0	12	0	0	7	0	0	2																	
OTU_45	159	21	130	6	29	0	0	0	41	12	1	0	0	1	0	12	0	3	0	15	8	0	66	40																		
OTU_49	48	11	83	101	46	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	17	0																		
OTU_19	163	39	24	44	24	4	15	0	2	82	3	9	0	15	14	0	34	0	11	0	22	16	0	2	66																	
OTU_174	31	0	22	3	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	2																		
OTU_103	58	21	39	4	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	7	8																		
OTU_29	248	26	153	5	12	0	0	0	9	7	0	1	0	4	2	0	8	1	2	0	37	9	0	20	23																	
OTU_38	204	76	102	33	10	0	0	0	22	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	4	0	2	1	0	21	51																	
OTU_74	62	17	41	10	21	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	5	2	0	1	15																		
OTU_14	30	0	9	0	0	0	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1																		
OTU_67	57	11	38	5	1	0	1	1	10	11	0	0	0	4	3	0	2	0	7	0	9	0	9	9																		
OTU_105	40	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2																	
OTU_27	79	0	939	3	164	0	6	0	3	52	3	15	21	148	98	0	622	0	28	385	907	0	198	130																		
OTU_1425	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																		
OTU_32	72	9	26	15	15	0	6	1	5	58	3	9	3	8	7	0	14	0	19	0	24	11	0	6	24																	
OTU_62	104	57	171	6	7	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	1	0	4	11																		
OTU_71	16	7	10	3	9	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	6	0	1	0	5	6	0	5	3																		
OTU_136	10	4	24	0	2	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	2	1																		
OTU_40	30	37	26	7	6	0	2	1	1	0	4	0	3	17	3	0	9	0	6	3	7	2	0	0	3																	
OTU_429	1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																		
OTU_75	24	0	12	7	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	0	5	0	2	3	0	3	5																		
OTU_84	68	5	73	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																	
OTU_182	14	0	39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0																		

scientific reports

OPEN

Monitoring of benthic eukaryotic communities in two tropical coastal lagoons through eDNA metabarcoding: a spatial and temporal approximation

Margoth L. Castro-Cubillos¹, Joe D. Taylor², Alicia Mastretta-Yanes^{3,4}, Francisco Benitez-Villalobos⁵ & Valentina Islas-Villanueva^{5,6,7}

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

16S

##OTU table file for 18S amplicons obtained from Chacahua-Pastoria and Corralero-Alotengo coastal lagoons##

OTUId	CD10	CD11	CD12	CD13	CD14	CD16	CD17	CD18	CD1	CD20	CD21	CD24	CD26													
OTU_155	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0													
OTU_6	252	173	328	233	4	2440	2019	1	0	3	73	38	858	2060	1366	0	46	5	602	105	569					
OTU_383	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	6	0	0	0				
OTU_57	66	33	66	5	12	2	8	2	0	35	1	3	0	2	0	0	1	0	3	0	77	20	0	1	4	
OTU_133	156	90	149	57	4	3	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	6	0	0	0	
OTU_64	331	518	14	3	34	0	0	0	5	0	1	0	1	48	3	0	133	0	0	62	249	23	0	5	0	
OTU_21	36	313	98	2	3	140	6	2	17	8	7	13	6	4	4	0	6	5	4	0	47	8	0	0	16	
OTU_4	317	154	144	6	2	40	8	13	3	96	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	1	9	0	0	64	
OTU_83	194	0	27	0	6	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1273	8	0	0	4	
OTU_973	17	1	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
OTU_16	25	371	29	33	1	1	35	3	0	10	4	31	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0	9
OTU_477	14	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
OTU_188	77	5	48	0	2	37	3	7	0	48	4	8	0	4	0	0	1	1	4	0	14	0	0	0	12	
OTU_39	97	672	64	1	0	1	1	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
OTU_212	7	657	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
OTU_2107	103	0	107	0	1	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	
OTU_538	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
OTU_109	121	203	149	10	7	26	6	9	2	53	2	0	0	2	1	0	4	1	2	13	4	5	1	0	4	
OTU_25	20	0	10	2	0	0	0	0	8	7	1	0	1	3	3	0	2	1	0	0	25	3	0	3	0	
OTU_224	47	0	0	6	8	0	0	0	1	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	80	0	0	22	0	15	0	0	0	
OTU_3469	1	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	
OTU_12	78	133	182	131	8	27	48	5	18	68	13	21	5	10	4	9	72	3	2	0	25	72	0	7	13	
OTU_317	24	45	1	0	0	2	0	9	0	0	0	0	12	0	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
OTU_164	23	403	44	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	
OTU_106	40	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	20	0	1	0	0	72	0	0	8	19	25	0	1	0	
OTU_48	25	19	38	14	1	0	0	1	9	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	9	1	0	2	5	
OTU_49	16	585	9	77	3	3	0	0	5	5	21	3	10	0	0	0	18	0	9	0	6	18	0	0	7	
OTU_104	58	900	10	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	12
OTU_604	2	0	11	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	
OTU_19	48	3691	128	4413	4	8	10	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	264	0	
OTU_74	17	107	37	15	11	34	20	15	3	7	6	0	2	4	0	8	13	0	0	8	54	11	0	0	0	

scientific reports

OPEN

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Margoth L. Castro-Cubillos¹, Joe D. Taylor², Alicia Mastretta-Yanes^{3,4}, Francisco Benitez-Villalobos⁵ & Valentina Islas-Villanueva^{6,4,6,8}

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

scientific reports

Taxonomic identification

OPEN

Monitoring of benthic eukaryotic communities in two tropical coastal lagoons through eDNA metabarcoding: a spatial and temporal approximation

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Table S3. New Reports. Results of NCBI BLAST for potential new records in the region.

Metazoan								
OTU ID	Description	Max. Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E. Value	Percentage Ident	Accession	Sequence
OTU_146	Amphibalanus eburneus isolate ES_ebur01 cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) gene, partial cds; mitochondrial	555	555	100.0%	7E-154	100.0%	MK240317	>OTU_146 TTTGTCAAGAAATATTGCACATTCTGGTGCTCTGTAGATCTCTCAATTTTCTCGCTTCACCTAGCCGGAGCA TTTAGGAGCAATTAATTTATATCAACAGTTAATAATATACGATCTGAAACTTAACTTTTGATCGTCTACCT GTTTGAAGAGTCTTTAATTACTGTAATCTACTCCTTTTATCATTACCTGTATTAGCAGGTGCTACTACTATATT
OTU_199	Macrothrix sp. HE-364 cytochrome oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene, partial cds; mitochondrial	551	551	100.0%	9E-153	99.7%	KC617066.1	>OTU_199 GTTAAGTAATTTGTCAGGCCATCCTGGTGCTGCCGTTGATATGGCAATATTTAGCCTGCACCTTGCAGGTAT TCTTAGGGGCAATCAATATGATTGTAACATATTTAACATGCGTGCTCCCGGAATGGGAATGTTCAAATAC >OTU_1120
OTU_1120	Calanus propinquus isolate CAPR3 cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (cox1) gene, partial cds; mitochondrial	538	538	100.0%	7E-149	99.0%	KC754433.1	ACTATCAAGTAATATTGCCATGCTGGAGCATCTGTAGACTTTGCTATTTTCTCCCTACATCTTGCCGGCGTA TTTGGGGGCGAGTTAATTTTATTAGGACACTGGGCAACTACGAGTATTCGGAATATTAATGGACCGAATA GCCTGAGCCGTTTTAATTACTGCCGTTTTAATCTACTATTATCTCTCCCGTATTAGCTGGGGCTACTACTATACT

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

Current analyses objects types:

- Low usage for eDNA and metabarcoding
- OTU/ASV table only stored and accessible as text file

Implementation of new analysis object - in test version

Analysis: ERZ483485

This record was produced by the EMBL-EBI Metagenomics (EMG) service as a Third Party Data set (TPA) identification table on ERR1467141. Four columns are provided, the first three directly from EMG, the fourth representing a taxonomic name-based mapping to NCBI Taxonomy.

Analysis Accession: ERZ483485
Analysis Type: SEQUENCE_ANNOTATION
Center Name: EMBL-EBI
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2020-10-15
ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2018-01-02

Analysis Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: [JSON](#) [TSV](#)

[Get download script](#)

[Download selected files](#)

[Download All](#)

Submitted files: FTP

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Analysis Accession	Analysis Type	Tax Id	Scientific Name	
PRJEB24173		ERZ483485	SEQUENCE_ANNOTATION			<input type="checkbox"/> ERR1467141_OTU.tab

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

ENA Metadata Model: Environmental Sequence Set

Analysis XML

Set of sequences in fasta format with information on frequency per sample (TSV format that provides the mapping between the sequences and the samples)

TSV

Sequence ID	sample	freq
PRJEB49250_ASV1	SAMEA11243268	14
PRJEB49250_ASV2	SAMEA11243267	13
PRJEB49250_ASV3	SAMEA11243268	18
PRJEB49250_ASV4	SAMEA11243259	4
PRJEB49250_ASV4	SAMEA11243264	97
PRJEB49250_ASV4	SAMEA11243266	4
PRJEB49250_ASV4	SAMEA11243267	5
PRJEB49250_ASV4	SAMEA11243268	5
PRJEB49250_ASV4	SAMEA11243270	1
PRJEB49250_ASV5	SAMEA11243259	8
PRJEB49250_ASV5	SAMEA11243261	8
PRJEB49250_ASV5	SAMEA11243265	3
PRJEB49250_ASV6	SAMEA11243260	30
PRJEB49250_ASV6	SAMEA11243270	8
PRJEB49250_ASV7	SAMEA11243268	24
PRJEB49250_ASV8	SAMEA11243259	2
PRJEB49250_ASV8	SAMEA11243261	5
PRJEB49250_ASV8	SAMEA11243265	8
PRJEB49250_ASV8	SAMEA11243266	12
PRJEB49250_ASV8	SAMEA11243268	1
PRJEB49250_ASV9	SAMEA11243268	14

```
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<ANALYSIS alias="ASVs from soil metabarcoding">
  <TITLE>ASVs from soil metabarcoding </TITLE>
  <DESCRIPTION>ASVs extracted from soil metabarcoding of marker x</DESCRIPTION>
  <STUDY_REF accession="PRJEB123456"/>
  <RUN_REF accession="ERR123456"/>
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    <ENVIRONMENTAL_SEQUENCE_SET/>
  </ANALYSIS_TYPE>
  <FILES>
    <FILE filename="soil_ASVs.fasta" filetype="fasta"
      checksum_method="MD5" checksum="95bfe45dced941cc2be9a34ca00325b"/>
    <FILE filename="soil_ASV_table.tsv.gz" filetype="tsv"
      checksum_method="MD5" checksum="95esdr45tfg6941cc2t6g7yhra00325b"/>
  </FILES>
  <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTES>
    <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <TAG>analysis_protocol</TAG>
      <VALUE>link to a document with the analyses protocol</VALUE>
    </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
    <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <TAG>Analysis date</TAG>
      <VALUE>2018-11-12</VALUE>
      <UNITS>YYYY-MM-DD</UNITS>
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  </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTES>
</ANALYSIS_SET>
```

Fasta

```
>PRJEB87286_ASV1
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTAITTTGCCAGAGACTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB87286_ASV2
GCTATGCTTAGCCATAAACCTAAATAATAATTAATTTAACAATAAATAITTTGCCAGAGAAGACTACTAGCCATAGCTTAAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB87286_ASV3
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTAITTTGCCAGAGAAGACTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAAACTCGAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB87286_ASV4
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTTAAACTCAACAGTTAAATCAACAAAAGCTGCTGCCAGACAAGACTACTAGCCATAGCTTAAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB87286_ASV5
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTTAAACTCAATAATTTAGAAAACAAAATTAITTTGCCAGAGAAGACTACTAGCCATAGCTTAAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB87286_ASV6
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>PRJEB87286_ASV7
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>PRJEB87286_ASV8
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTAITTTGCCAGAGAAGACTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
```

Data Submission at ENA

Data Submission at ENA

- There are three submissions routes
- *'Interactive Submission'*:
 - Use your browser to fill out web forms describing your work
- *'Programmatic Submission'*:
 - Describe your work in XML documents, submit them to us using cURL
- *'Webin-CLI'*:
 - Smart submission interface, made in-house

Data Submission: Interactive

- Register your objects using your browser
- Familiar and largely accessible
- Prepare spreadsheets for bigger submissions

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
22-05-2024

Study Name
Arabidopsis mutation accumulation

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

Short descriptive study title *
Testing de novo mutation calling artefacts by re-sequencing single mutation accumulation

Detailed study abstract *
To test for the possibility that mutation bias results could in part be artifacts of a pooled-seedling sequencing approach, we re-sequenced entire rosettes of siblings (individual plants) of one mutation accumulation line and asked if the distribution of variation called (i.e., putative somatic mutations around transcription start and termination sites) was similar to the patterns seen with the seedling pools of the 107 individual lines described in the preceding section. Specifically, we grew 10 siblings and extracted DNA from 3-week old whole rosettes. Barcoded PCR-free libraries for

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedid	Title	Remove
9784120	Arabidopsis thaliana: a model plant for genome analysis.	

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MIXS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample derived from	collection date	geographic location (country and/or sea)	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude) by
3	#units								DD	DD
4										
5										

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type									
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5
3												
4												

Data Submission: Programmatic

- Prepare an XML/JSON file describing your submission
- Send this to us via HTTPS
- Correct format for JSON/XML files important for successful submission and validation of data.

- Example cURL command:

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SAMPLE=@sample.xml" \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

```
<SUBMISSION>  
  <ACTIONS>  
    <ACTION>  
      <ADD/>  
    </ACTION>  
  </ACTIONS>  
</SUBMISSION>
```

```
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</SAMPLE_SET>
```


ENA - Submission Tools & Data Portals

eDNA Data Submission

eDNA Data Submission: Webin Portal

Welcome to the Webin Submissions Portal

You can use this service for a range of submission activities as well as reports on your submissions. For help with submitting your data, including the use of this interface, please refer to our Help Guides. Please familiarise yourself with the different options available. New users are advised to take a moment to understand the interface.

Studies tab

Used for registering studies and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered studies

Samples tab

Used to register new samples, requesting taxonomy for novel/unidentified/published species and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered samples

Raw reads/experiments tab

Used to register runs/experiments and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered runs/experiments

Can also be used to track run files validation/processing

Studies (Projects)

Studies Report

- + Register Samples
- + Register Novel Taxonomy
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

Samples

Samples Report

Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)

- + Submit Reads
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

- Runs Report
- Run Files Report
- Run Processing Report
- Unsubmitted Files Report

Data Analyses

Assemblies and annotated sequences must be submitted with **Webin-CLI**. Other analyses can be submitted as XMLs.

- + Generate Annotated Sequence Spreadsheet
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)
- Analyses Report
- Analysis File Report
- Analysis Processing Report

Analyses tab

Used to download annotated sequences template spreadsheet and view submitted analyses metadata.

Can also be used to track analyses files processing.

eDNA Data Submission: Webin Account

- Each submission requires a Webin account.
- Can be created by submitting web form on the Webin Portal page.
- Requires fields such as centre name, country and user credentials.
- Fields such as centre name, contact information can be updated.
- Metagenomics consent box to allow MGnify to access and analyse metagenomic data.

Account Details

Abbreviated center name	Password
Full center name	Confirm Password
Laboratory Name	
Address	
Country	

Contact Information

Add At Least One Contact

No Sensitive Data

I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.

Metagenomics Consent

By keeping this box checked you give consent to the EBI MGnify team to analyse those data for which you have requested a pre-publication confidential hold. Note that the data as well as the analysis results will remain confidential until the specified release date of the associated sequencing study. If you are also requesting assembly of your data by MGnify, you also give consent to MGnify to submit these assemblies to your ENA study on your behalf. MGnify will not change any metadata or data you have already submitted but may need to perform updates to submissions performed by their team in exceptional circumstances. This service provides pre-publication state-of-the-art analysis results, along with visualisations, that you may use in subsequent publications. The service is described in <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/31696235> and we kindly request, should you use these analyses in your publications, that you cite this paper.

I give consent and confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable

Save Cancel

eDNA Data Submission: Study

- Study required for each submission at the ENA.
- Needs to be registered interactively or programmatically (XML or JSON format). Webin-CLI does not support study registration.
- Umbrella projects only submitted programmatically.
- Groups data objects under one project.
- Authority on release date of data objects linked to a study.
- Add publications and study attributes to study metadata.

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Short descriptive study title

Study Name

Detailed study abstract

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration
Add PubMed Citations

Study Attributes
Add Study Attributes

Submit Cancel

```
<PROJECT_SET>
  <PROJECT alias="cheddar_cheese">
    <NAME>WGS Streptomyces iranensis</NAME>
    <TITLE>Characterisation of Microbial Diversity and...</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>This study aimed to characterise the interaction of microbial...</DESCRIPTION>
    <SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
      <SEQUENCING_PROJECT>
        </SEQUENCING_PROJECT>
      </SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
    </PROJECT>
  </PROJECT_SET>

{
  "submission": {
    "alias": "",
    "accession": "",
    "actions": [
      {
        "type": "ADD"
      },
      {
        "type": "HOLD",
        "holdUntilDate": "2026-10-12"
      }
    ]
  },
  "projects": [
    {
      "alias": "Plantdiversity",
      "name": "Plant diversity metabarcoding",
      "title": "Plant diversity in mediterranean fo",
      "description": "study abstract",
      "sequencingProject": {},
    }
  ]
}
```

eDNA Data Submission: Samples

- Samples can be registered interactively, programmatically or with Webin-CLI.
- Programmatic submissions both in JSON or XML format
- Webin-CLI submissions in JSON format
- Range of sample checklists to choose from including Environmental, Pathogen, Plant and Marine checklists.
- Include required, recommended and mandatory metadata fields.
- Mandatory minimum metadata fields for all checklists include taxonomy information, sample details, collection dates and geographic location.

```
"samples": [
  {
    "alias": "uniqueAlias",
    "title": "human gut microbiota, mucosal",
    "organism": {
      "taxonId": "408170"
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "project name",
        "value": "human gut study"
      },
      {
        "tag": "collection date",
        "value": "2010-01-20"
      },
      {
        "tag": "host body site",
        "value": "Mucosa of stomach"
      },
      {
        "tag": "human-associated environmental package",
        "value": "human-associated"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (latitude)",
        "value": "1.81",
        "unit": "DD"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (longitude)",
        "value": "-78.76",
        "unit": "DD"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
        "value": "Colombia"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (region and locality)",
        "value": "Tumaco"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environment (biome)",
        "value": "Coast"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environment (feature)",
        "value": "human-associated habitat"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environmental medium",
        "value": "gastric fluid"
      },
      {
        "tag": "broad-scale environmental context",
        "value": "human gut"
      },
      {
        "tag": "local environmental context",
        "value": "human gut"
      },
      {
        "tag": "ena-checklist",
        "value": "ERC00013"
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

```
{
  "study": "PRJEB12345",
  "sample": {
    {
      "alias": "sediment_sample",
      "title": "Sample derived from sediment in Antarctica",
      "organism": {
        "taxonId": "77133"
      }
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "collection date",
        "value": "2025-01-30"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
        "value": "Antarctica"
      },
      . . .
    ]
  },
  "name": "ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-28-10-2024-01:02:26:880-109",
  "platform": "ILLUMINA",
  "instrument": "Illumina MiSeq",
  "insert_size": "390",
  "libraryName": "unspecified",
  "library_source": "GENOMIC",
  "library_selection": "PCR",
  "libraryStrategy": "AMPLICON",
  "fastq": {
    "value": "test_single_run_2.fastq.gz",
    "attributes": {
      "read_type": ["single"]
    }
  }
}
```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC00013	GSC MixS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample derived from	collection date	geographic location (country and/or sea)	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude) br
3	#units							DD		DD
4										
5										

eDNA Data Submission: Run

- Raw reads may be submitted interactively, programmatically (XML or JSON file formats) and using Webin-CLI (plain text or JSON formats)
- For interactive and programmatic submissions run files must be uploaded before submission
- Supports several file formats including Fastq, BAM, CRAM, HDF5 and FAST5 (but only BAM, CRAM and Fastq file formats are supported by Webin-CLI).
- Webin-CLI validates files before submission.
- Successful submission returns a run accession with the sequence files metadata and an experiment accession with the library metadata.

Programmatic - JSON

```

"experiment":{
  {
    "alias":"exp_amtis_religiosa",
    "centerName":"EBI",
    "title":"The IKITE project:evolution of insects",
    "study":{
      "accession":"SRP017801"
    },
    "samples":{
      {
        "accession":"SRS462875"
      }
    },
    "designDescription":"",
    "libraryDescriptor":{
      "libraryName":"unspecified",
      "libraryStrategy":"RNA-Seq",
      "librarySource":"TRANSCRIPTOMIC",
      "librarySelection":"cDNA",
      "libraryLayout":"paired"
    },
    "instrumentPlatform":"ILLUMINA",
    "instrumentModel":"Illumina HSeq 2000",
    "attributes":{
      {
        "tag":"library preparation date",
        "value":"2010-08"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

manifest.txt

```

STUDY ERP013289
SAMPLE ERS980556
NAME ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-13-03-2025-01:02:26:880-109
INSTRUMENT Illumina MiSeq
INSERT_SIZE 390
LIBRARY_SOURCE GENOMIC
LIBRARY_SELECTION PCR
LIBRARY_STRATEGY AMPLICON
FASTQ test_single_run.fastq.gz

```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type									
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5
3												
4												

eDNA Data Submission: Analysis

- Environmental Sequence Set can be submitted programmatically using a curl command or through the Webin Portal
- Webin-CLI submission route is under implementation
- Supports fasta format for sequences and TSV format for ASV/OTU tables
- Additional analysis metadata provided in the submission XML/JSON
- Successful submission returns analysis accession. During processing individual accessions are assigned to each sequence

```
curl -u username:password -X POST
'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H
'Accept: application/xml' -H 'Content-Type: application/xml'
-T 'submission file name'
```

Sequence_id	Sample_id	Frequency
PRJEB49250_ASV1	SAMEA11243260	30
PRJEB49250_ASV10	SAMEA11243261	9
PRJEB49250_ASV10	SAMEA11243259	13
PRJEB49250_ASV11	SAMEA11243260	23
PRJEB49250_ASV12	SAMEA11243259	3
PRJEB49250_ASV12	SAMEA11243261	5
PRJEB49250_ASV12	SAMEA11243260	25
PRJEB49250_ASV13	SAMEA11243260	16
PRJEB49250_ASV14	SAMEA11243259	8
PRJEB49250_ASV14	SAMEA11243261	10
PRJEB49250_ASV15	SAMEA11243260	9
PRJEB49250_ASV15	SAMEA11243259	2991
PRJEB49250_ASV15	SAMEA11243261	3289
PRJEB49250_ASV16	SAMEA11243260	11
PRJEB49250_ASV17	SAMEA11243261	5
PRJEB49250_ASV17	SAMEA11243259	12
PRJEB49250_ASV18	SAMEA11243260	23
PRJEB49250_ASV19	SAMEA11243260	12
PRJEB49250_ASV2	SAMEA11243260	10
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243259	8
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243261	10
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243260	23
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243260	11
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243260	16
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243259	28
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243261	28
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243260	18
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243260	19
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243260	10
PRJEB49250_ASV20	SAMEA11243259	16
PRJEB49250_ASV28	SAMEA11243260	23
PRJEB49250_ASV28	SAMEA11243261	23

```
<ANALYSIS_SET>
<ANALYSIS alias="ASVs from soil metabarcoding">
  <TITLE>ASVs from soil metabarcoding </TITLE>
  <DESCRIPTION>ASVs extracted from soil metabarcoding of
  <STUDY_REF accession="PRJEB123456"/>
  <RUN_REF accession="ERR123456"/>
  <ANALYSIS_TYPE>
    <ENVIRONMENTAL_SEQUENCE_SET/>
  </ANALYSIS_TYPE>
  <FILES>
    <FILE filename="soil ASVs.fasta" filetype="fasta"
    checksum_method="MD5" checksum="95ebfe45dced94
    <FILE filename="soil ASV_table.tsv.gz" filetype="t
    checksum_method="MD5" checksum="95esdr45tfg694
  </FILES>
  <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTES>
    <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <TAG>analysis_protocol</TAG>
      <VALUE>link to a document with the analyses pr
    </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
    <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <TAG>Analysis date</TAG>
      <VALUE>2018-11-12</VALUE>
      <UNITS>YYYY-MM-DD</UNITS>
    </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
```

```
>PRJEB87286_ASV1
ACTATGCTTAGCCTTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTTTGGCCAGAGAGC
>PRJEB87286_ASV2
GCTATGCTTAGCCATAAACCTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTTTGGCCAGAGAG
>PRJEB87286_ASV3
ACTATGCTTAGCCTTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTTTGGCCAGAGAGC
>PRJEB87286_ASV4
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACCTCAACAGTTAAATCAACAAAATGCTCGCCAGAGAGC
>PRJEB87286_ASV5
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACCTCAATAATTTAAGAAACAAAATTTTGGCTGAGAGAGC
>PRJEB87286_ASV6
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACCTCAATAATTTAAGAAACAAAATTTTGGCCAGAGAGC
>PRJEB87286_ASV7
ACTATGCTTAGCCTTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATTTTGGCCAGAGAGC
```

eDNA Submission: Upload data files

- For Interactive and programmatic submissions data files (raw read sequence files or fasta and tsv files) need to be uploaded to Webin account before submission.
- Can use multiple tools to upload files using FTP or Aspera.
- Runs and analysis can be submitted after upload.

Programmatic Data Submission: APIs

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/>

- XML file format submissions
- Synchronous endpoint
- Submit one data object in one file

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin-v2/>

- XML and JSON file format submissions
- Synchronous and asynchronous endpoints
- Submit multiple data objects in one file

eDNA Data Submission

Summary

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

- The ENA provides **scientific record** of sequencing data.
- Established in the early 1980s, extended for **new technologies and applications**.
- Comprehensive record of world's **nucleotide sequencing information** covering raw read data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation.
- Presents large amounts of a diverse range of data in a consistent manner, making use of **data and metadata Models**.
- Metadata model requires minimal mandatory metadata in line with **FAIR data principles**.
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**.
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training.
- **Data submission** routes: Interactive, programmatic and Webin-CLI.
- **eDNA data** submission with new analysis object for OTU/ASV tables - in testing phase.
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals.

Handy links

- ENA Browser: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>
- ENA Submission/Retrieval Guide: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>
- ENA Helpdesk: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/support>
- Advanced Search: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>
- Webin Reports API: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/report/swagger-ui/index.html>
- Webin Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>
- Webin TEST Portal: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

**Thank you
Any Questions?**

eDNA Data Submission Practical

During this exercise, you will implement some of the skills you have just learnt and submit some eDNA data to the ENA.

1. Register a study programmatically
2. Register your samples using a spreadsheet
3. Submit runs programmatically
4. Submit an environmental sequence set object programmatically

Thank you
Any Questions?

